

Factors Affecting Happiness Learning of Students of Faculty of Management Science, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University

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Abstract—The objectives of this research are to compare the satisfaction of students, towards the happiness learning, sorted by their personal profiles, and to figure out the factors that affect the students' happiness learning. This paper used survey method to collect data from 362 students. The survey was mainly conducted in the Faculty of Management Science, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, including 3,443 students. The statistics used for interpreting the results included the frequencies, percentages, standard deviations and One-way ANOVA. The findings revealed that the students are aware and satisfaction that all the factors in 3 categories (knowledge, skill and attitude) influence the happiness learning at the highest levels. The comparison of the satisfaction levels of the students toward their happiness learning leads to the results that the students with different genders, ages, years of study, and majors of the study have the similar satisfaction at the high level.

Keywords—Happiness Learning, Satisfaction, Students.

I. INTRODUCTION

SUAN Sunandha Rajabhat University has had proficient educational management in a unified system which include providing advice, design and development services, hardware and software, equipment and systems operations. These activities aim to meet the needs of target group or customers of educational institutions, financial institutions and banks. Because the university provides the students with multiple skills and capabilities, they will work effectively within any organizations and with others.

Currently, the education system in Thailand focuses on producing good students with mentally and physically healthy. In doing so, educational institutions should pay attention to both an intelligence quotient and an emotional quotient. Teachers and related persons in educational institutions should create a positive environment for students' learning in the classroom.

According to the eleventh national economic and social development plan 2012-2016 [1], its vision is "A happy society with equity, fairness and resilience." This plan aims to increase the potential of Thai people based on a holistic approach that enables physical, mental, intellectual, emotional, ethical and moral development through social institutions. Thus, Thais can live happily. This concept is consistent with

happiness learning in terms of to make people being quality and good citizens as well as living happily together.

As discussed above, the factors affecting happiness learning among the students of Management Science Faculty was conducted. The present study aims to compare the satisfaction toward happiness learning and to study the factors that influence happiness learning among students of the Management Science Faculty, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Concept of Happiness Learning

The education today aims to produce quality students to become good citizens who are mentally and physically healthy in order that they can live with others happily. Therefore, teachers are important persons who can make the students to have such qualifications. Teachers need to create an atmosphere for happiness learning. The happiness learning is to create a relaxed atmosphere in which the students feel free and easy to involve themselves into the classroom activities. The teachers must accept and understand the differences among students in order that students can develop their learning potentials.

To create an atmosphere of happiness learning is very beneficial for students, for both current and future success. The advantages of happiness learning are as follows:

- 1) It can help students have a good mental and physical health that can lead them living with others happily.
- 2) It will promote self-directed and lifelong learning among students because they enjoy learning and feel independent to how their opinions in the classroom.
- 3) The students who are learning in the atmosphere of happiness will be kind-hearted and helpful persons.
- 4) The students will have high self-esteem and a will power to do good things.
- 5) The students can learn how to live with others; they will accept, understand, and sympathize with others who are different from them.

The happiness learning focuses on learning what the students are interested in; so that they will learn happily. Learning by doing is also one of techniques in happiness learning; they can integrate their ideas and the story to learning process. Moreover, teachers can integrate body movement, music, and arts into the learning process in order to make students happy. When students are happy, their brains

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will release dopamine, a feel-good chemical; they will also eager and enjoy learning new things. Interestingly, happy students can learn and remember things better than unhappy ones. In terms of memory, it is very essential to the learning process. The more people remember, the better they can learn.

The happiness learning is influenced from both external and internal factors. The external factors that influence happiness learning consist of teachers and parents who create a positive environment for learning. The internal factors affecting happiness learning are students themselves who are happy inside. When being happy, they will enjoy learning things both inside and outside the classroom.

B. The Concept of Factors that Influence Learning

Thailand has adjusted and adapted itself into a knowledge-base society. Education is one of the most important factors to develop the nation. The effective education system can lead the nation to the success because educated people can think and act effectively and reasonably. Dr. Kriengsak Charoenwongsak [2] noted that there are five main factors that influence the education systems: (1) technological factors, (2) economic factors, (3) bureaucratic factors, (4) political factors, and (5) cultural factors. All the five factors are considered to set up the education policy.

First of all, the technological factors are vital for educational development. The education system today needs to adapt and apply modern technology to the learning process. Second, the education system should be designed to respond to the need of labor market. Thus, the students should learn what the current job market wants. Third, the bureaucratic factors sometimes hinder the development of the education because of its slow and inflexible operation. Thus, teachers, education personals, and related parties should adapt themselves to changing environment. Next, the political factors are the most influential factors that affect the education system. There have been fifteen ministers of education in the past sixteen years, meaning that each minister was in the position just for a short time; therefore, the education plan was not run continuously and effectively. Finally, Thais rank the importance of maintaining good relationship much higher than the achievement value, hard working; such value might hinder the development of the education.

C. The Concept of Learning Theory

The notion of learning theory is about the process that can change individual's behavior, thought, and capability. Humans can learn from their experiences by hearing, touching, or doing things. To the students, they mainly learn in the classroom by doing, asking questions, and participating with others while teachers act as a facilitator of learning process. Therefore, teachers have to create relaxed learning environment in order that the students will have positive attitude of learning.

When a person has learned something there will be changes as following (Bloom) [3].

1) Cognitive Domain means the learning process about the new content will make learners know and understand their

environment more clearly. This change will happen in the brain area.

- 2) Affective Domain means when a person has learnt something new, this will affect them mentally, and will affect their beliefs and interests.
- 3) Psychomotor Domain, which means that when a person has learnt a thought process, comprehension grows which allows those ideas to be applied to practice, and makes the person more skillful/ proficient in physical tasks: for example the usage of hands.

The significant components that cause learning from Gagne's [4] Taxonomy of Learning are as follows;

- 1) The learner has an intellectual skill to learn.
- 2) Stimulus is the situation that prompts learners to learn.
- 3) Response is the behavior that occurs from the learning.

Teaching Machines through Gagne's concepts are;

- 1) To stimulate the learners, provide a program that interests the learners, including using comics, graphics or pictures that attract them.
- 2) Curiosity will motivate the learners to be interested in lessons, asking questions will too.
- 3) To inform learners of learning objectives, making them aware of the outcomes of their learning.
- 4) To stimulate the memories of learners by building new ideas on their own existing knowledge. This will cause the long term memory for learners by questioning the concept of content.
- 5) Presentation. This process introduces content to learners by using various materials including pictures, graphics, sound or videos.
- 6) Giving examples, by presenting case studies, or showing comparisons for deeper understanding.
- 7) Practice Stage, this will encourage skills and behaviors. It is also to measure the learners' understanding in order for teachers to repeat again, or try different ways of reinforcing new knowledge if the learners misunderstand something.
- 8) Giving additional explanations for examples giving learners exercises with the provided explanations.
- 9) Giving tests to measure levels of understanding.
- 10) To apply this for the media production, you should have some extra contents or necessary titles.

1. Cognitivism [5]

The cognitivists started broadening the framework for understanding the mind that was focused on behaviors of the thinking process (which are processes which happen inside the brain). They believe that the learning of humans is not the process that only happened from the response to the stimulus as had been previously suggested by the behaviorists. They argued that human learning was way more complicated than that. Learning is the process caused by collecting data, defining meanings and making relations of the data and applying that information into actions and to solve problems. Learning is the intellectual process of human beings in order to obtain knowledge and understanding.

2. Learning and Teaching Principals

- 1) The thinking process is an important process for learning. To learn how to encourage the thinking process, therefore, is necessary and essential to help learners understand and learn by themselves.
- 2) Being taught by giving the whole concept to learners before giving them the smaller details, will make them learn better.
- 3) To encourage learners to have lots of experience, having gained various experiences will help learners to be able to think, to solve problems and be more creative.
- 4) To manage new experiences to link with their own previous experiences will help learners to learn new things better and more easily.
- 5) To manage the stimulus for learners to learn well is to put the same kind or similar stimuli in the same category.
- 6) When teaching, teachers don't need to present the whole perfect content, teachers can choose only some important parts if they are sure the students can fulfill the content with their own related experience.
- 7) To teach lessons or any content, teachers should order the contents in a smooth, progressive way, linking one learning criteria to the next so that students can learn better and faster.
- 8) Encouraging students to experience diversity in ideas will allow learners to grasp bigger concepts more easily.

D. Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory [6]

Piaget studied the cognitive development of children and described them in many stages and how those stages worked. He added that the learning method of children was a progressive reorganization of mental processes as a result of biological maturation and environmental experience. This development should be processed naturally and follow the learning stages. We shouldn't encourage children to skip one step to another because it will cause more disadvantage to children. However, to help provide experiences that encourage children's gradual development into the higher stages will help children to develop faster. Piaget focused on understanding the nature and the development of children more than motivating them to have the faster development.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. The Objectives of This Research

1. To compare the satisfaction toward the happiness learning of students of the Management Science Faculty, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, sorted by different genders, ages, years and majors of study; and
2. To study on the factors influencing the happiness learning of students of the Management Science Faculty, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University.

B. Research Hypotheses

Based on literature review, the following hypotheses have been derived:

1. The students of the Management Science Faculty, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, with different personal

profiles are significantly different in satisfaction toward happiness learning.

2. The factors affecting happiness learning will relate to satisfaction toward happiness learning.

C. Research Framework

Research framework, as seen in Fig. 1, was actually drawn from many high impact papers that offer very interesting theories concerning satisfaction and the researcher has chosen Kotler [7] to be used as the main model for designing a questionnaire. In addition, a sample was designed by using ideas from Taro Yamane [8].

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

D. Sampling Technique

The population used in this study was the students who are studying at the Management Science Faculty, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University including 3,443 students [9]. The Management Science Faculty offers courses in business administration, accounting business administration, and communication arts at the undergraduate level.

The faculty offers the most subjects for students to choose from the university with 17 areas of study, including Bachelor of Administration Program includes 8 majors in Business Economics, Human Resource Management, Business Computer, Finance and Banking, Entrepreneurship, Marketing, Business Service Management, and International Business. Bachelor of Accountancy Program includes only one major; accountancy. Bachelor of Communication Arts program contains 8 majors; Journalism and Information Technology, Public Relations and Corporate Communication, Advertising and Marketing Communication, Television Broadcasting, Radio Broadcasting, Film and Performing Arts, Animation and New Media Communication, and Animation and Multimedia.

Sample was selected by using convenience sampling. A questionnaire was applied to collect data; totally, 362 usable questionnaires were received.

IV. FINDINGS

The findings indicated that the students with different genders, ages, education years and majors have similar levels of satisfaction toward happiness learning at high level. The results also showed that students with different genders, ages, education years and majors were not significantly different in satisfaction toward happiness learning. All the factors that influence happiness learning, i.e., skills, attitudes and knowledge, can cause the satisfaction toward happiness learning among students of the Management Science Faculty, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University.

V. DISCUSSION

The purposes of this study were to compare the satisfaction toward happiness learning and to examine factors that influence the happiness learning among students of Management Science Faculty, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The results indicated that the satisfaction toward happiness learning among students were at high level. The students with different genders, ages, education years and majors were not significantly different in satisfaction toward happiness learning. In addition, the factors influencing happiness learning—skills, attitudes, and knowledge—can lead to the satisfaction toward happiness learning among the students.

Agreeing with Pattama Thongsom [10], she studied about happiness indicators of learning among students in nursing science undergraduate programs under the Ministry of Public Health. The results revealed that the composite indicators of happiness learning consist of 5 composite indicators: satisfaction in learning, eagerness in learning, professional attitude, satisfaction in themselves, and anxiety respectively. The results also showed that the students in nursing science undergraduate programs had average of happiness learning in high level.

The findings from the research show that the coefficient of the attitude aspect is the greatest of the three factors, which means that the attitude has the greatest impact on the students' satisfaction toward the happiness learning [11]. Therefore, the administrative of the university should pay attention to the form of learning management in order to make the learning process happier and more fun, which will encourage students to pay attention to what they are learning. This will increase the level of students' satisfaction toward the learning.

Concerning the skill, the administrative should emphasize the designing of the course that encourages teachers to be always eager to learn and pass on new knowledge to the students. Teachers should introduce new sources of knowledge to their students and emphasize communication and interaction by allowing students to have conversations with them in order that students can ask them questions about the lessons [12]. Students should also be allowed to exchange their knowledge with their teachers and peers.

In terms of the knowledge aspect, the administrative of the university should set the curriculum that fits the diversity of students. The course should integrate all the relevant bodies of

knowledge in order that students can learn more and have a better outcome in learning process [13].

VI. SUGGESTIONS

From the results of the studies, there are some suggestions as follows:

1. The further studies should cover additional factors that affect the happiness learning, such as opinions toward the learnt subjects, physical and mental health, motivations, and readiness of students, creativity and enjoyment of the lessons and so on.
2. The factors that affect students' happiness learning should be examined in a longer period of time because a short period study might not reveal precise results. The studies in longer periods might clearly reflect the real factors that affect students' happiness learning.

VII. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE STUDIES

There were some limitations of this study. Firstly, the sampling technique used was convenience technique that is nonprobability sampling. The results might not be generalized to the population. Thus, the future study should apply probability sampling to collect data from sample. Secondly, the future research should study broader perspectives of happiness learning. Finally, the future study should examine factors that influence happiness learning from both teachers and students; it might have a broader body of knowledge regarding happiness learning.

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